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ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE**SAIDOVA Shakhnoza Aripovna**
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PATHOGENETIC RATIONALE FOR THE NECESSITY OF REINFUSION OF ASCITIC FLUID IN PATIENTS WITH LIVER CIRRHOSIS

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17087691>**ABSTRACT**

Liver cirrhosis is a serious disease, being the 11th most frequent cause of death worldwide, with 50% of patients dying within 5 years. Ascites in cirrhosis develops as a result of various pathogenetic factors: hyperaldosteronism, fluid accumulation in the body, portal hypertension, increased lymph production and impaired outflow, reduced drainage function of the parietal peritoneum, autoimmune dysproteinemia, and disturbance of plasma colloid-oncotic balance. Modern medicine offers several methods for treating ascites, including drug therapy, serial laparocenteses with removal of large volumes of fluid, transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunts, implanted drainage devices, as well as acellular and concentrated reinfusion therapy. Each of these approaches has its advantages and limitations, and choosing the optimal treatment strategy often presents a challenging task. This article discusses modern methods of ascites treatment using reinfusion with the Fresenius preparation.

Keywords: ascitic fluid, albumin, liver cirrhosis, lymphatic system.

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ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВАНИЯ НЕОБХОДИМОСТИ РЕИНФУЗИИ АСЦИТИЧЕСКОЙ ЖИДКОСТИ У БОЛЬНЫХ ЦИРРОЗОМ ПЕЧЕНИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цирроз печени — тяжелое заболевание, занимающее 11-е место в списке наиболее частых причин смерти в мире: 50% пациентов умирают в течение 5 лет. Асцит при циррозе развивается вследствие различных патогенетических факторов: гиперальдостеронизма, накопления жидкости в организме, портальной гипертензии, повышенной продукции и нарушенного оттока лимфы, снижения дренажной функции париетальной брюшины, аутоиммунной диспротеинемии, нарушения коллоидно-онкотического равновесия плазмы. Современная медицина предлагает несколько методов лечения асцита, среди которых медикаментозная терапия, серийные лапароцентезы с удалением больших объемов жидкости, трансъюгулярные внутривенные портосистемные шунты, имплантируемые дренажные устройства, а также бесклеточная и концентрированная реинфузионная терапия. Каждый из этих подходов имеет свои преимущества и ограничения, и выбор оптимальной стратегии лечения зачастую представляет собой сложную задачу. В статье рассматриваются современные методы лечения асцита с использованием реинфузии препаратом Фрезениус.

Ключевые слова: асцитическая жидкость, альбумин, цирроз печени, лимфатическая система.

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JIGAR SIRROZI BILAN OG‘RIGAN BEMORLARDA ASTSITIK SUYUQLIKNI REINFUZIYA ZARURATINING PATOGENETIK ASOSLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Jigar sirrozi jiddiy kasallik bo‘lib, dunyo bo‘ylab o‘limning eng ko‘p uchraydigan sabablari orasida 11-o‘rinda turadi, bemorlarning 50% 5 yil ichida vafot etadi. Sirozdagi astsitlar turli patogenetik omillar natijasida rivojlanadi: giperaldosteronizm, organizmda suyuqlik to‘planishi, portal gipertenziya, limfa ishlab chiqarishning ko‘payishi va chiqishining buzilishi, parietal peritonning drenaj funksiyasining pasayishi, autoimmun disproteinemiya va plazma kolloid-onkotik muvozanatning buzilishi. Zamonaviy tibbiyot astsitlarni davolashning bir necha usullarini taklif etadi, jumladan dori terapiyasi, katta hajmdagi suyuqlikni olib tashlash bilan seriali laparosentezlar, transyugulyar ichki jigar portosistemik shuntlash, drenaj qurilmalarini implantatsiya qilish, shuningdek hujayrasiz va konsentrlashgan reinfuzion terapiya. Ushbu yondashuvlarning har biri o‘zining afzalliklari va cheklovlariga ega va optimal davolash strategiyasini tanlash ko‘pincha qiyin vazifani keltirib chiqaradi. Ushbu maqolada Fresenius preparati bilan reinfuziya yordamida astsitni davolashning zamonaviy usullari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: astsit suyuqlik, albumin, jigar sirrozi, limfa tizimi.

Liver cirrhosis is a disease characterized by diffuse proliferation of connective tissue with the formation of regeneration nodules that arise due to hepatocyte necrosis, which disrupts the lobular structure of the organ [1]. The main etiological factor of liver cirrhosis is hepatitis B and C viruses. Among 25% of hepatitis B virus carriers, there is an increased risk of developing severe liver

pathology, and in 20% of patients infected with hepatitis C virus, liver cirrhosis develops within 5 years. Ascites syndrome develops in 25-85% of patients with liver cirrhosis. From the moment of its appearance, the patient's life expectancy does not exceed 5 years. The presence of ascitic fluid in the abdominal cavity significantly worsens the functional state of the liver and other organs and systems of the body [2]. The pathogenesis of ascites syndrome is complex and not fully understood. The main role in the development of ascites is played by portal hypertension and impaired catabolism of hormones and other biologically active substances in the liver, hemodynamic changes (increased cardiac output, decreased systemic vascular resistance, decreased blood pressure, increased renal vascular resistance), and water-electrolyte imbalance (sodium and water retention). Several studies indicate the lymphogenous origin of ascites in liver cirrhosis [5,6]. Under normal conditions, there is a balance between lymph formation in the liver and its adequate outflow [2]. In pathology, this balance is disrupted, leading to lymphatic edema of the hepatic parenchyma.

With intrahepatic and suprahepatic block of portal blood flow, lymph production in the liver increases. As a result, the hepatic lymphatic vessels expand and collaterals open: lymph production increases sevenfold, the number of collaterals - threefold. Lymph production and structural changes in the lymphatic system depend on the duration and severity of hemodynamic disorders, indicating the organic and functional unity of lymph and blood circulation [2,3,4].

The lymphatic system performs an important compensatory function and is considered as a second drainage system [5]. By resorbing proteins, metabolites, and fluid, the lymphatic vessels free the hepatic tissue from harmful products, minimize hypoxia, improve trophism, and prevent fibrosis of the organ. The compensatory-adaptive development of the abdominal lymphatic system in response to fluid accumulation manifests as enlargement and changes in the lymph nodes and the network of lymphatic anastomoses. Within one hour, 80% of the ascitic fluid is renewed. This indicates the high resorptive capacity of the abdominal wall, i.e., the formation of the so-called porto-hepato-lympho-ascito-lympho-caval mechanism of fluid purification and drainage [2,6,7].

Ascitic fluid is a fluid that has passed through hepatocytes and the lymph nodes of the liver. Due to the dialyzing abilities of the abdominal cavity, the ascitic fluid becomes cleaner than the lymph of the thoracic duct. Decompensation of the abdominal lymphatic system and, accordingly, a decrease in resorptive function leads to the formation of refractory ascites [3,6].

Purpose of the work: to study the change in serum albumin of ascitic fluid and the possibility of using ascitic fluid for autoreinfusion in patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis.

Materials and methods:

Sixteen patients with liver cirrhosis and portal hypertension in the decompensation stage were examined, including 10 men and 6 women (mean age 52.7 years). The diagnosis was verified according to the classification of chronic hepatitis and liver cirrhosis [8]. The control group consisted of 10 practically healthy volunteers.

In the blood serum of practically healthy individuals and in the blood serum and ascitic fluid of patients with liver cirrhosis, albumin fractions were determined by electrophoresis in polyacrylamide gel in the presence of sodium dodecyl sulfate [4], and its content in ascitic fluid and blood serum was measured by enzyme immunoassay [11].

The total amount of albumin in ascitic fluid was calculated based on the volume of ascitic fluid using the methylene blue dilution method [9].

Analytical isoelectric focusing of albumin was performed in 5-6% polyacrylamide gel [9]. The completion of focusing was judged by the migration and concentration of dye zones with known isoelectric points. After completing the electrofocusing, part of the gel was stained to reveal protein zones, while another part was used to measure the pH gradient.

The binding capacity of albumin in ascitic fluid and blood serum was determined by gel filtration. The amount of furosemide and propranolol bound to albumin was measured using high-performance liquid chromatography [9].

Statistical processing of the obtained data was performed using Student's t-test.

Results and discussion

Our study demonstrates that regardless of the volume of ascitic fluid, the albumin level fluctuates within the range of 219.41±6.43 g. The binding capacity of albumin in ascitic fluid with furosemide is 1.5 times higher, and with propranolol 2 times higher, than the binding capacity of albumin in blood serum (Table № 1). The ascitic fluid of patients with liver cirrhosis contains a significant amount of albumin with preserved ligand-binding capacity, which does not differ from the capabilities of serum albumin in healthy individuals.

Serum albumin represents the sum of albumins with different isoelectric points. Therefore, studying the ratio of isoelectric fractions of albumin allows us to assess its functional characteristics in liver pathology [10,11].

The isoelectric fractions of serum albumin in healthy individuals are predominantly located in zones № 2 (83%), № 1 (7.8%), and № 3 (6.4%).

Table № 1. Binding capacity of serum albumin in healthy individuals and serum albumin (numerator) and ascitic fluid (denominator) with furosemide and propranolol in patients with liver cirrhosis, P1<0.0001, P2<0.0001

Examined	Albumin, mg/ml	Furosemide binding to 1 ml of fluid, µg	Furosemide binding to 1 ml albumin, µg	Albumin mg/ml	Binding of propranolol to 1 ml of fluid, µg	Binding of propranolol to 1 ml albumin, µg
Healthy	57.10±2.74	144.82±4.73	2.55±0.08	54.89±12.0	206.49±0.47	3.77±0.18
Patients	39.78±1.29	63.14±2.63	1.59±0.07	44.68±2.48*	85.78±6.52	1.91±0.008
	13.90±1.14	38.16±3.34	2.74±0.009	15.76±1.29	55.99±4.76^	3.55±0.008

Note. P1 – reliability of differences with the indicators in healthy individuals. P2 – with the indicator in blood serum. * - P1<0.02, ^ - P1<0.01.

This is explained by the fact that the maximum load on albumin in the metabolic process is the binding and transport of “indirect” bilirubin and its biotransformation in hepatocytes.

We analyzed the content and ratio of isoelectric fractions of serum albumin in healthy individuals and patients with liver cirrhosis in ascitic fluid in a comparative aspect (Table 2).

Table 2. Isoelectric fractions of albumin in blood serum of healthy individuals and in blood serum (numerator) and ascitic fluid (denominator) of patients with liver cirrhosis, P<0.0001

Examined	Albumin fractions, % of total amount by zones				
	Zone №1, pH 4.2	Zone №2, pH 4.7	Zone №3, pH 5.1	Zone №4, pH 5.5	Zone №5, pH 6.5
Healthy	7.82±0.44	82.68±1.81	6.43±0.27	2.14±0.08	1.16±0.11
Sick	1.23±0.08	93.80±2.33*	0.79±0.03	1.94±0.009**	2.42±0.14
	5.33±0.23	85.54±2.55^	3.96±0.15∨	2.89±0.11∨	1.57±0.07∨

Note. P – significance of differences compared to the control group. * - p<0.01, ^ - p<0.05, ∨ - p<0.02, ** - p=0.02.

In patients with liver cirrhosis, the albumin content in zone No. 1 is reduced by 6 times, in zone No. 3 - by 8 times, while its relative content in zone No. 5 is increased by 2 times and in zone No. 2 - by 12.8% (Table 2). The disproportion of isoelectric fractions of serum albumin in patients is likely associated with functional loads on albumin for binding and transporting excess bilirubin and ammonia.

Apparently, the restoration of the imbalance of pH-dependent albumin fractions in the ascitic fluid is due to their "cleansing" in the lymphatic system and partly in the functioning hepatocytes. In total, the isoelectric fractions of ascitic fluid albumin in zones № 1 and № 2 reach 96%. Consequently, the isoelectric spectrum of ascitic fluid albumin in patients and serum albumin in healthy people are identical. Probably, the lymphatic system has its own metabolic mechanisms, to a greater extent bilirubin and to a lesser extent other xenobiotics. Therefore, the pH-dependent ratio of the albumin fraction is restored.

Undoubtedly, there is an "intermediate" system that restores the properties of albumin. This is probably the lymphatic "detoxification" system.

Thus, ascitic fluid is a multicomponent biological environment that includes the same chemically active substances as plasma and lymph. Functionally, ascitic fluid albumin is more complete than serum albumin. Due to the dialysis capabilities of the peritoneum, the content of many toxic substances and nitrogenous wastes in this fluid is lower than in blood plasma and lymph.

The intravascular administration of ascitic fluid, which has an antiatherogenic effect, helps improve the properties of cell membranes, including hepatocytes, as well as correct hemorheological disorders. The powerful lymphostimulating effect helps eliminate interstitial edema and improve microlympho- and microhemocirculation. Against this background, oxidative tissue metabolism increases, contributing to the cessation of cytolytic processes in the liver and reducing endogenous intoxication [2,7,12].

In many clinics worldwide, in the search for the most accessible, effective, economical, and least dangerous methods of managing cirrhotic ascites, the possibilities of reinfusing ascitic fluid, including its detoxification, are being studied [2,7,12]. We used a reinfusion model with concentration of ascitic fluid, developed at the Scientific Center of Gastroenterology, using F-5 and F-6 "Fresenius" hemodialyzers. A total of 48 procedures were performed, averaging 6-7 per patient, at intervals of 1.5-3 months. As a result of treatment, the patients' condition stabilized, signs of hepatic encephalopathy disappeared, and laboratory test results normalized within 7-12 days (Table № 3).

Table 3. Results of laboratory blood tests in patients with liver cirrhosis in the decompensation stage depending on the time after reinfusion of ascitic fluid.

Indicator	Before reinfusion	After reinfusion, 24 hours	
		1-2nd	3-5th
ALT, U/L	0.8	0.7	0.6
AST, U/L	0.7	0.5	0.5
Bilirubin, µmol/l			
general	38	31	27
direct	9	6	4
indirect	29	25	23
Total protein	66	71	72
Albumin, g/l	29	34	35
Potassium, mol/l	3.5	3.9	4.1
PTI	68	70	71

In all patients, blood coagulogram parameters significantly improved, electrolyte imbalance normalized, and blood acid-base balance stabilized. Glomerular filtration increased, episodes of cardiovascular insufficiency were resolved, and the progression of general dystrophy slowed down.

Conclusions:

1. In patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis, the albumin of ascitic fluid is functionally more complete than serum albumin and closer in its isoelectric spectrum to the serum albumin of healthy individuals.
2. Reinfusion of ascitic fluid is a pathogenetically justified treatment method for patients with liver cirrhosis complicated by refractory ascites.
3. As a result of autoinfusion of ascitic fluid in patients with liver cirrhosis, blood biochemical parameters improve, the severity of hepatic encephalopathy decreases, and recurrences of new ascites develop at later stages.

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